

Studies on Charge Transfer Complexes with Alicyclic-*n*-donors

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Spectrophotometric study of the charge transfer interaction of chloranil and bromanil with piperazine, morpholine, piperidine and some methyl substituted piperidines has been carried out in chloroform. The spectral data and the effect of solvent on the complexes have been reported and discussed. The ionisation potential of donors has been evaluated. Half width of charge transfer band, oscillator strength, transition dipole moment, *a*, *b* values, percent charge transfer and percent ionic character values have been computed for the complexes.

STUDY on charge transfer (CT) complexes has been gaining attention over the past few decades. These studies are of importance in that they may lead to an understanding of the physicochemical phenomena, dominated by molecular interactions involving intermolecular forces. The behaviour of molecules extending from the relatively simple activity change to the conservation and transmission of the genetic code^{1,2}, also may be due to such intermolecular forces for which, although theoretical advances have been made and sophisticated experimental techniques are available, we still have to depend on model compounds. With this in view Muralikrishna and coworkers³⁻¹⁰ undertook a study of CT complexes and the present study extends to those of alicyclic-donors with chloranil and bromanil, in chloroform medium.

Experimental

Chloranil (CA) (E. Merck) and bromanil (BA) prepared from hydroquinone¹¹ are recrystallised twice from acetone. Donors are all obtained from Fluka A.G. Piperazine (PZ) is used as it is, whereas morpholine (ML), piperidine (PD) and methyl substituted PDs are further purified by distillation. Stock solutions of both donors and acceptors are prepared by dissolving in chloroform (B.D.H., spectroscopy grade). They are suitably diluted as and when needed. The absorption spectra are run, mixing equimolar concentrations of donor and acceptor, after complete formation of the complex (maximum absorbance). Pye Unicam SP 700A recording spectrophotometer is used with matched, stoppered silica cells of 1 cm path length at 30°. The solvents used for the study of solvent effect are sufficiently pure.

Results and Discussion

The distinct change in the colour on mixing the components indicates the complex formation in

solution. The new absorption bands, not observed in either of the components, are characteristic^{1,2} of CT complexes^{1,2}. Further, the absorption maxima and the energy associated with the absorption (Table 1) indicate the transitions to be of $n-\pi^*$ type. The identical behaviour with both the acceptors may be due to their similar electron affinity (1.37 eV)^{14,15}. The composition of the complexes, employing Job's method of continuous variation¹⁶,

TABLE 1—ABSORPTION MAXIMA [λ_{CT}] AND EXCITATION ENERGY [$h\nu_{CT}$] FOR THE COMPLEXES WITH CHLORANIL AND BROMANIL IN CHLOROFORM

Donor	With CA		With BA	
	λ_{CT} nm	$h\nu_{CT}$ eV	λ_{CT} nm	$h\nu_{CT}$ eV
Piperazine (1)	578	2.143	578	2.143
Morpholine (2)	572	2.165	570	2.171
Piperidine (3)	576	2.150	576	2.150
4-Methyl piperidine (4)	576	2.150	575	2.154
3-Methyl piperidine (5)	576	2.150	575	2.154
2-Methyl piperidine (6)	578	2.143	578	2.143
N-Methyl piperidine (7)	588	2.106	587	2.110
3,5-Dimethyl piperidine (8)	576	2.150	576	2.150
2,6-Dimethyl piperidine (9)	582	2.129	582	2.129

is found to be 1 : 1 and is verified by the mole ratio method¹⁷ also. The effect of methyl substituent on PD is almost identical^{18,19}, as expected for the aliphatic compounds. However, in case of 2-methyl and 2,6-dimethyl PDs the adjacent electron releasing substituent to the donation site favours the donating ability of PD and hence λ_{CT} reduces considerably. N-Methyl piperidine (NMPD), a tertiary amine, where the electron releasing substituent is directly attached to the nitrogen atom and the enhanced basicity resulted in a CT in the lower energy region. The results in Table 2 indicate that the λ_{CT} is non-dependent on the dielectric constant of the solvent⁷. The small low energies of the CT observed in the

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TABLE 2—SOLVENT EFFECT ON THE λ_{CT} OF THE COMPLEXES USING BROMANIL AS ACCEPTOR
(Donors are indicated with numbers as in Table 1)

Solvent	Dielectric constant	λ_{CT} , nm								
		(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
n-Hexane	1.9	564	552	563	563	563	563	582	563	567
Cyclohexane	2.1	570	560	569	568	568	570	584	569	573
Carbon tetrachloride	2.2	562	550	560	560	560	562	690	560	566
Benzene	2.3	573	561	570	570	571	572	586	570	576
Chloroform	4.8	578	570	576	575	575	578	587	576	582
Dichloromethane	9.1	574	568	573	572	572	575	585	572	579

polar solvents are due to the fact that the dative structure of the complex, which is predominant in the excited state, is relatively stabilised^{20,21} in these solvents. Further, it can be seen that NMPD in carbon tetrachloride behaves in a peculiar way, which may be due to the solvent effect²². Solvent molecules are known to interact with excited states and such interactions are rather strong in CT systems²³.

Bregleb and Czekalla²⁴ described a method of determining the ionisation potential, I^D , from the frequencies of the CT bands of the complexes. Such linear relationships between I^D and the $h\nu_{CT}$ of the complexes were widely discussed by many authors^{7,25-28}. The calculation methods using such relationships may provide a simple means of estimating I^D , which may be difficult to determine by other methods like Rydberg series, photoionisation and electron impact, because of the low vapour pressures of some of these substances²⁹. I^D values for the present donors have been calculated using the following equations:

$$\text{with chloranil}^{26} \quad h\nu_{CT} = 0.89 I^D + 5.13 \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\text{with bromanil}^{30} \quad h\nu_{CT} = 0.97 I^D + 5.27 \quad \dots (2)$$

The values are recorded in Table 3. The I^D values of PD is in good agreement with the literature values (7.4 eV⁷, 7.7 eV³¹). The transition dipole moment (also referred as the intensity of the CT band) is directly proportional to the stability of the complex³² and is calculated from:

$$\mu_{en} = 0.0958 [1.505 \epsilon \Delta\nu/\nu]^{1/2} \quad \dots (3)$$

and the oscillator strength, f is calculated from:

$$f = 4.32 \times 10^{-9} \times 1.505 \epsilon \Delta\nu \quad \dots (4)$$

TABLE 3—IONISATION POTENTIAL OF THE DONORS (I^D) USING THE $h\nu_{CT}$ OF THE COMPLEXES FORMED WITH CHLORANIL AND BROMANIL IN CARBON TETRACHLORIDE

(Donors are indicated with numbers as in Table 1)

Donor	I^D , eV	
	Using OA ⁻	Using BA
(1)	7.60	7.54
(2)	7.66	7.59
(3)	7.61	7.55
(4)	7.61	7.55
(5)	7.61	7.55
(6)	7.60	7.54
(7)	7.15	7.12
(8)	7.61	7.55
(9)	7.57	7.52

where $\Delta\nu$ is the half width of the CT band in cm^{-1} and ϵ is the molar absorptivity, taken as a measure of the intensity of the absorption band.

The dipole moment of CT complex, μ_{CT} , %CT, % ionic character (Λ) of the complex can be computed from the following equations³³:

$$a^2 + b^2 + 2abS = 1 \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\mu_{CT} = \mu_1 (b^2 + abS) \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\%CT = 100(b^2 + abS) \quad \dots (7)$$

$$\text{and} \quad \Lambda = 100 b^2 / (a^2 + b^2) \quad \dots (8)$$

By assuming the overlap integral (S)³³ and using appropriate value for the dipole moment, μ_1 in the excited state³⁴ from the literature, the calculated values are recorded in Table 4.

The data indicate that the complexes formed with alicyclic secondary amines are stronger than those with aromatic amines.

TABLE 4—HALF WIDTH OF THE CT BANDS $\Delta\nu$, MOLAR ABSORPTIVITY ϵ , OSCILLATOR STRENGTHS f , TRANSITION DIPOLE MOMENTS μ_{en} , a , b VALUES, CT COMPLEX DIPOLE MOMENTS μ_{CT} , %CT, AND % IONIC CHARACTER Λ VALUES FOR CT COMPLEXES (IN CHCl_3)

Complex	$\Delta\nu$ cm^{-1}	ϵ^* $\text{lit mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	f	μ_{en} debyes	a	b	μ_{CT} , debyes	%CT	% Λ
CA.PZ	5020	1820	0.0594	2.69	0.840	0.302	2.98	19.3	11.40
CA.ML	5030	1260	0.0412	2.63	0.826	0.323	3.24	21.2	13.30
CA.PD	5280	4480	0.1540	4.34	0.932	0.148	1.18	7.7	2.46
BA.PZ	4490	1430	0.0435	2.30	0.847	0.291	2.81	18.3	10.60
BA.ML	4940	1120	0.0360	2.09	0.817	0.336	3.42	22.3	24.50
BA.PD	4950	2950	0.0980	3.37	0.879	0.244	1.59	14.3	7.00

* The values are reported separately³.

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